

ANCIENT WORLD MUSIC PERFORMANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7312302>

Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the history of the creation of early musical instruments, the appearance of musical instruments, and the procedure for using musical instruments in various ceremonies.

Keywords: music, culture, ancient, tradition, musical instruments, celebration, ritual.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация об истории создания ранних музыкальных инструментов, появлении музыкальных инструментов, порядке использования музыкальных инструментов в различных обрядах.

Ключевые слова: музыка, культура, древность, традиция, музыкальные инструменты, праздник, ритуал.

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада дастлабки мусиқа чолғу асбобларининг яратилиш тарихи, чолғу асбобларнинг кўриниши, турли хил маросимларда чолғу асбоблардан фойдаланиш тартиби ҳақида батафсил маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: мусиқа, маданият, қадимги, анъана, чолғу асбоблари, байрам, сурнай, най, маросим.

The Uzbek Center for the Study of Cultural Heritage Abroad and the Center for New History of Uzbekistan are being set up. Great attention is paid to the development of reading culture, culture and art, and creative schools and centers named after our great artists are being established in the regions. Systematic measures are being taken to further popularize folklore and amateur arts, and to develop innovative areas of culture and the arts. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "If culture and art do not develop in the country, society will not develop. It is important to develop the field of culture and arts, to increase the prestige of the Uzbek national culture and art in the world, to realize the potential of young talents. Indeed, when art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole of humanity, live in peace".[1]

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 " On measures for

innovative development of the arts ”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “ On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan”, 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 “ On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021”, November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 “ On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House-Museum” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [2] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay ”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “ Kokand ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [3] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [4], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Martyrs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD – 1 2 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [5] are becoming increasingly important.

It should be noted that the music of ancient times is also the most important factor in knowing our history.

As a result of their protection and household needs, ancient people invented instruments that are louder than the human voice and are played in the open air, and it is customary to use them in hunting, to send messages and signals to other tribes, in military campaigns, at weddings, feasts, festivals and other various gatherings. entered Examples of musical instruments found in fossils of the Paleolithic (12-15 thousand years BC) have reached our time.

Most of them are percussion instruments. In the 3rd-1st centuries BC, the instruments were described as flute-like, tongue-and-trumpet-like, two-stringed and multi-stringed harps. As a result of the unification and growth of tribes and peoples, the first states of Bactria, Sagdiyone and Khorezm appeared in the territory of our country, the military-administrative unification of the Achaemenids, and the emergence of the Greco-Bactrian administration under the campaigns of Alexander the Great. This period includes a huge historical process from the 7th century BC to the 4th century AD. During the time of

Alexander the Great, drums, trumpets and drills of various sizes were used to keep the troops moving in an orderly manner and to terrify the enemy.[6]

According to one legend, Alexander said to Plato: "Make such an instrument that its sound can be heard from a distance of fourteen miles, and it will strike fear and terror into the hearts of the enemy". After thinking about it, Plato covered both sides of the big box with cowhide and pulled it taut and made a blind drum. A blow from one side of the drum resonated with the skin on the other side, and shouted, "Iskander! Alexander!" - he made a terrible sound. It is from this that the creation of all drums and hurricanes with leather on both sides of the present era is left. The miniature below shows the battle between the armies of Alexander and Darius, and the background of the Persian army is a picture of a trumpeter and a trumpeter, known as an elbow leaf. He calls his army to battle with a battle cry and thunders into the heart of the enemy. During this period, the names and deeds of legendary folk heroes were sung as legends, narratives, stories and epics. Among them, Shirok's unparalleled bravery and love for the motherland were reflected in the epic about him, while Tomaris' selflessness is greater and more sacred than the defense of the homeland, which was told in the epic associated with his name. Also, legends, narratives and epics related to the names of Rustami Doston, Sièvush, Sukhrob, Afrosiyob and similar sacrificers were passed from mouth to mouth among the people. Later, some of these epics were preserved.[7]

According to the historical documents, during these periods, among the villages were "Kaikhisravi", "Qinni Eroj", "Qinni Siyovush", "Bogi Shirvan", "Bogi Shahriyor", "Navruzi Buzrug", "Navruzi kuchak", "Gulzor", "Mehrijan", It is described that there were tunes and songs such as "Shabdiz", "Dilnavaz". By the time of the reign of Khusrau Parvez II (590-628 years) (the capital is the city of Mari, present-day Turkmenistan), culture flourished.

Skilled musicians, singers, dancers, and artists from different parts of Movaraunnakhr gathered in his palace: Sarkash, Bamshad, Nokus, Romitin, Fitna, Navogar, Sarkab, Ozodvor Changi and Robusts are among them. Among them, Borbad Marvazi (also known as Fakhliz or Fakhlobod) stood out as a particularly bright star. During his career, Borbad created and performed 360 songs, 30 songs. Among them are the "Khusravani" series, "Ov Gashti", "Chashtgoh", "Sarvzor", "Oy sokiniligi", "Shirin Bogi", "Ruh yullari", "Sarviston", "Jamshid mirror", The names of 148 such as "Pearl Umbrella" are still mentioned in the sources.

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